

Appraisal of the Fishing Communities' Means of Subsistence along Shiroro and Kainji Dams, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study appraised the Fishing Communities' Means of Subsistence along Shiroro and Kainji Dams, Nigeria. *Questionnaire was used to collect data from 460 respondents. Multi-stage and proportionate sampling techniques were used in selecting the respondents. Descriptive statistics were used for data analysis. Livelihood assets mostly possessed by the fishers were access to water body with a mean $\bar{x} = 4.66$ and access to agricultural land $\bar{x} = 3.61$. These activities and assets promote efficient fishing and farming activities among the fishers. Coping strategies adopted by the fishers indicated that informed financial planning decisions with a mean $\bar{x} = 4.61$ and diversification into new activities $\bar{x} = 4.60$ were the most adopted coping strategies by the fishers to attain more income for sustained livelihood conditions. In conclusion, the study showed that, artisanal fisheries activities are an important livelihood activity in the lives of the fishers as it enhances food security and income of fishers. The study therefore recommended that Trainings and seminars on livelihood diversification strategies should be provided by private organizations with the necessary support of the government. This will enlighten the fishers on how best to distribute their eggs among baskets and withstand shock that could arise from the failure of their major livelihood source. Government should also make formal credit available at one digit interest rate. More extension officers should be recruited by government to provide more extension services to fishers that could boost artisanal fisheries practices around the two dams and in the country at large.*

Keywords: Fishing Communities, Subsistence, Shiroro Dam, Kainji Dam, Nigeria, Livelihood, Fisheries

OVERVIEW

Because it generates money, high-quality protein, and contributes to the socioeconomic development of fishing villages in Nigeria, the fisheries subsector of Nigerian agriculture is a vital tool for rural development (Adepoju and Abayelu, 2013). Due to the benefits that Nigerians receive from fish and other fish products, as well as the subsector's importance to the country's economy, there is a significant demand for fishery products. The federal government of Nigeria has executed a number of initiatives aimed at augmenting the local fish supply with great success. According to Degefa (2017), some of the initiatives include the second and third stages of the Fadama programs. While there have been some gains noted in terms of fish output level, the usage of conventional fishing methods has resulted in an ongoing disparity between the supply and demand for fish. It is impossible to overstate the significance of the fishing industry to people's lives and the economies of many industrialized and developing nations. It is noteworthy that fish, particularly in poorer nations, accounts for about 60.0% of global protein intake. Nigerians living in both rural and urban areas could sense its significance both directly and indirectly (Dasuki *et al.*, 2014).

The many small-scale, low-tech, low-capital fishing techniques used by individual fishing households are collectively referred to as artisanal fishing. Local systems made up of professional small-scale coastal fishing communities define artisanal fishing, which has significant economic, social, and cultural importance (Arowolo *et al.*, 2022). Because of the rich biodiversity that the water bodies have historically provided, they have developed a high level of professional competence as well as a culture and customs that have been passed down from generation to generation. Because artisanal fishing uses a variety of gear and ways to harvest different types of resources, it is a multi-specific industry. Furthermore, it is difficult to fully characterize artisanal fishing since it is a very complex system that interacts with the environment and other socioeconomic sectors (Alinovi *et al.*, 2010).

The issue of artisanal fishermen's rural livelihoods is changing, particularly in developing economies due to the region's weak agricultural systems, rising rates of poverty, hunger, and starvation, and economic regression (Ellis, 2000). In accordance with Amurthiya's (2015) scholarly research, a livelihood consists of the capacities, resources, and pursuits necessary for subsistence. Additionally, he said that a livelihood is sustainable if it can withstand shocks and strains, preserve or improve its assets and capacities, and offer possibilities for a sustainable living. Therefore, a livelihood consists of individuals, their capacities, and their means of subsistence, including income and assets. It also consists of sufficient stocks and flows of food and money to meet fundamental demands of life. The assets may be of a material or immaterial kind. Physical resources are considered tangible assets, whereas claims and access are considered intangible assets (Edward and Frank, 2001). In light of this, the study provided answers to the following research questions.

1. What are the livelihood assets possessed by the artisanal fishers?
2. What are the coping strategies employed by the artisanal fishers?

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. Assess the livelihood assets possessed by the artisanal fishers
2. Identify the coping strategies employed by the fishers

METHODOLOGY

Description of Shiroro Dam

The study was carried out along Shiroro and Kainji Dams. The population of Shiroro is projected in 2020 to be 322,918 people using 3.2% growth rate (Bryceson, 2016). The climate, edaphic features and hydrology of the state allows sufficient opportunities for harvesting fresh water fish such as *Tilapia* spp, *Bagrus* spp, *Clarias* spp, *Gymnarchus niloticus*, *Heterotis* spp, *Labeo* spp, *Mormysus* spp, *Latesniloticus*, and permit the cultivation of most of Nigeria's staple crops such as maize, yam, rice, millet and sorghum. The Shiroro hydropower reservoir is a storage based hydroelectric facility located in Shiroro Local Government, Niger State at the Shiroro Gorge with approximately between Latitude 9° 57' 25N and Longitude 6° 49' 55E. It is located approximately 90 km southwest of Kaduna on River Dinya. About 70% of inflows into the reservoir are from river Kaduna, with lateral contributions from rivers Dinya, Guni, Sarkin-Pawa, Erena and Muyi. Annual temperature around the reservoir varies between 27 and 35⁰C (Asaku, 2017).

Description of Kainji Dam

Kainji Lake is located between latitudes 9°5' and 10°55'N and longitudes 4°21' and 4°45'E. It cuts across the Niger and Kebbi states, and is mostly located in Niger state. Kainji is the second largest lake in Africa and the largest man-made lake in Nigeria (Asiedu and Francis, 2013). It was created in 1968 following the impoundment of the Niger River by the construction of the Kainji Dam at New Bussa, in Borgu Local Government Area of Niger State.

The highest (about 30°C) and the lowest (about 25°C) monthly temperatures are recorded in March and August, respectively. Fishing is the major traditional occupation of these people whereas other occupations include: farming, livestock breeding and local entrepreneurship such as pottery, mat weaving, gear/craft making and servicing (Ellis, 2000).

Method of Data Collection

Both primary and secondary data were used for the study. Primary data was obtained using structured questionnaires designed in line with the study objectives. The copies of which were administered to the respondents selected for the study. Secondary data were collected from relevant text books, internet data bases, journal articles, seminar documents, conference papers, annual reports and other relevant materials.

Data Analysis Procedure

Livelihood Assets

Capital assets (natural assets, human assets, physical assets, social assets and financial assets) enumeration was used to analyse objective 1 and was done by rating respondents on the quality of livelihood assets using Likert scale of Excellent (abundant assets base) - coded 5, very good (progressive) - 4, good (sustainable assets base) - 3, poor (constrained assets base) - 2 and very poor (unsustainable assets base) - 1. Based on their responses, any score below the mean (3.00) indicated weak and restricted livelihood assets status while a score of 3.00 and above indicate otherwise.

Coping Strategies

Likert scale was used to analyse objective 2 (the livelihood strategies adopted by the fishers). This scale falls under the criterion group instruments whereby items are collected and analyzed against a criterion. Each item has a weight or score attached to it. A person's score

on the final attitude scale is simply the sum of the weight of the alternatives he has checked. Weights are usually assigned to those high scores which indicated favorable attitude.

Likert's type of scale was adopted to analyze the livelihood coping strategy adopted by the fishers.

The important positive statements and scores assigned are;

Strongly agreed.....	5
Agreed.....	4
Undecided.....	3
Disagreed	2
Strongly disagreed	1

While for negative statements and the scores assigned are:

Strongly disagreed.....	1
Disagreed.....	2
Undecided.....	3
Agreed.....	4
Strongly agreed.....	5

Where average mean score = $\frac{\text{Total sum of perception score}}{\text{Total number of respondents}}$

$$\text{The mean score} = \frac{\sum fxi}{N} = \frac{5+4+3+2+1}{5} = 3$$

Then an arbitrary number of 0.5 was added to 3.0 to obtain 3.5 while 0.5 was subtracted from 3.0 to obtain 2.5 for negative statements. Hence, the important positive statements were all those from 3.5 and were considered as favourable statements while the negative statements were those below 3.5 and were considered as unfavorable statements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Livelihood Assets Possessed by the Fishers in the Study Area (n = 460)

Livelihoods assets	Mean	Std. Deviation
Natural assets		
Access to water body (fishing ground)	4.66*	0.61
Fisheries resources	2.02	0.47
Access to agricultural land	3.61*	0.89
Forest resources	2.48	0.84
Access to mineral deposit	1.69	0.75
Seasonal benefit had from the climate	2.25	0.66
Human assets		
Health status	2.43	0.64
Family labour (skilled)	2.64	0.83
Educational status (formal)	1.71	0.61
Skill / capacity in other livelihood	2.28	0.68
Physical assets		
Ownership of building / housing	2.35	0.72
Possession of fishing gears and craft	1.92	0.57
Presence of good infrastructure / social amenities	1.47	0.54
Possession of modern household appliances	2.07	0.43

Social assets		
Social network	2.91	0.65
Membership of association	2.50	0.78
Access to market	1.96	0.77
Access to community leaderships	2.61	0.87
Access to hospitals	2.15	0.66
Financial assets		
Remittances	2.19	0.69
Access to credit	1.68	0.74
Investment worth	1.95	0.76
Cash elsewhere (lend)	2.36	0.73
Cash at hand	1.22	0.47

Source: Field Survey, 2023

**Good (mean ≥ 3.00)*

Table 2: Likert's Type Scale Showing the Livelihood Strategies Adopted by the Fishers (n = 460)

Coping Strategy	SA	A	UD	DA	SD	Total	Average mean scores
1. Intensification of the existing income activities	284	154	10	8	4	2086	4.53* (Favourable)
2. Diversification into new activities	294	152	12	0	2	2116	4.60* (Favourable)
3. Migration to areas with perennial water supply	255	195	4	4	2	2077	4.51* (Favourable)
4. Diversifying means of credit access	2	0	2	116	340	588	1.30 (Unfavourable)
5. Drawing up social Relations	4	2	4	170	280	660	1.43 (Unfavourable)
6. Petty trading	258	194	6	0	2	2086	4.53* (Favourable)
7. Food vending	2	6	13	183	256	695	1.51 (Unfavourable)
8. Informed financial planning decisions	293	162	3	1	1	2125	4.61* (Favourable)

Source: Field Survey, 2023. *Good (mean ≥ 3.00)

Key: SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, UD = Undecided, SD = Strongly Disagreed, D = Disagreed

Livelihood Assets Possessed by the Fishers

Table 1 was used to analyse objective 1. It reveals the livelihood assets possessed by the fishers. Assets are stocks of direct and indirect productive factors that produce a stream of cash and endowments. The livelihood asset-base of the fishers considered for the study include; natural assets, human assets, physical assets, social assets and financial assets as shown in Table 4.8. The distribution revealed that majority of the respondents fell between

poor (constrained) and good (sustainable) assets from all the categories enumerated. The result revealed that respondents' access to fishing ground ($\bar{x}=4.66$, $SD=0.61$) and agricultural land ($\bar{x}=3.61$, $SD=0.89$) was sustainable. This is significant in promoting active fishing and farming livelihoods in the study area. Further analyses shows that respondents operate below sustainable educational status ($\bar{x}=1.71$, $SD=0.61$). This is significant in the kind of non-fishing livelihoods that fishing households could be engaged in. Respondents show low level of skill and capacity in other livelihoods ($\bar{x}=2.28$, $SD=0.68$). This is a major entry requirement for non-fishing livelihoods.

Infrastructure/social amenities ($\bar{x}=1.47$, $SD=0.54$) were abhorrently inadequate and absent in most of the communities. This implies that they are disconnected and have no access to infrastructure/social amenities that could improve livelihood opportunities. This explains the total absence of the three tiers of government in most of the fishing communities. The community members travel for a distance of not less than 10km to access health care facilities. There were no schools in over 90.0% of the fishing communities' in spite of government effort on achievement of basic primary education for Nigeria. Most of the fishers lamented on their state of abandonment with respect to schools, hospitals, road networks and electricity. Socially, most (80.0%) of the assets enumerated were near sustainable level. This indicates that there is strong social cohesion in fishing communities and is known to rely heavily on social network for livelihood improvement. This according Chilaka *et al.*, (2013) implies that social network allows the development of organized structures for non-subsistence activities, adequate to compensate for restriction in livelihood assets and provide diverse employment and income generation. In respect of financial assets, about 60.0% of the assets enumerated were unsustainable. This remains a fundamental problem among fishing households that wish to diversify from fishing to non-fishing livelihoods.

Livelihood Strategies

Table 2 was used to analyse objective 2. It indicates the Likert type scale showing the livelihood coping strategies adopted by the fishers in the study area with the corresponding average mean. It reveals the strategies adopted by the fishers in order to earn more income to sustain livelihood conditions in the study area. The strategies used by fishers can be seen as an expression of decision to minimize the effect of factors influencing livelihood activities in the area towards a sustained livelihood condition (Amurtiya, 2015). The result in table 4.9 shows the strategies adopted by fishers in the study area. A group of fishers who strongly supported that Intensification of the existing income sources ($\bar{x}=4.53$) as coping strategy towards enhanced sustainable livelihood activities in the study area thereby generating more income to offset household financial obligations.

Diversification into new activities had a mean ($\bar{x}=4.60$) suggesting that this group of fishers engaged in other livelihood activities apart from fishing in order to cope with livelihood conditions imposed by the current economic realities in the country. This study is in agreement with the findings of Asaku (2017) who reported that majority of the respondents with a mean of ($\bar{x}=4.70$) diversified into other income generating activities in order to meet household financial needs of food/dietary needs, clothing and shelter provision. The result further indicated that petty trading ($\bar{x}=4.53$) and informed financial planning decisions ($\bar{x}=4.61$) were adoption by these group of fishers as livelihood strategies that greatly had an effect on their livelihood in the study area. Similarly, respondents that fell within the Unfavourable statements include those that believe that drawing up social relations ($\bar{x}=1.43$) and food vending ($\bar{x}=1.51$) will enhance livelihood sustainability in the area. It is very clear from the table that diversification into new activities and informed financial

planning decisions were the majority coping strategies adopted by the respondents. This is closely followed by intensification of the existing income sources and petty trading. Diversification into new activities and intensification of the existing income sources will help generate more income to the fishers thereby assisting in coping with livelihood conditions (Aruwajoye and Ajibefun, 2013). The coping strategies adopted by the respondents had an effect on their livelihood sustainability, implying that the coping strategies were very effective in coping with livelihood activities.

Conclusion / Recommendations

In conclusion, the fishermen's primary means of subsistence were their proximity to bodies of water and their possession of agricultural land, both of which encouraged productive farming and fishing practices. The fishermen's chosen coping mechanisms revealed that the most popular ones for increasing income and ensuring a stable standard of living were financial planning and diversification into new endeavors. It is advised that private groups, with the required backing from the government, offer trainings and seminars on livelihood diversification techniques. The fishermen will get knowledge from this on how to divide their eggs across baskets and prepare for any shock that may result from the loss of their main source of income. Formal credit should be made available by the government at a one-digit interest rate. The government should hire more extension officers to give fishermen more services that could improve artisanal fishing methods near the two dams and throughout the nation.

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